

THE RIVER FOREST

Conservation, restoration and governance
of Mediterranean riparian forests

index

1. HEAD INTO THE FOREST
2. FUNCTIONS OF THE RIVER FOREST
3. THE ALTERATION OF THE NATURAL STATE OF THE RIVER FOREST
4. THE LIFE ALNUS PROJECT
5. CHALLENGES FOR THE FUTURE
6. GLOSSARY
7. RECOMMENDED READING

Authors: Jordi Camprodon, Pol Guardis and Marc Ordeix
Published by: Forest Science and Technology Centre of Catalonia (CTFC)

The following people have collaborated in the preparation of this publication: David Guixé, Víctor Sazatornil, Arnau Picó, Jaime Coello, Míriam Piqué, Virgilio Hermoso, Mónica Lanzas, Xavier Florensa, Robert Manzano, Helena Navalpotro, Laura Torrent, Carles Durà, Lluís Bertrams and Ferran Oró (CTFC); Evelyn Garcia, Antoni Munné, Albert Rovira, Emilio Sánchez, Jordi Tuset, Mònica Bardina and Alfredo Pérez (Catalan Water Agency); Èlia Bretxa, Rosa Gurí, Laia Jiménez, Marta Jutglar and Núria Sellarès (Centre for the Study of Mediterranean Rivers [CERM]-University of Vic-Central University of Catalonia); Guillermo García, Roger Pascual, Oda Cadiach, Adrià Balart, Jaume Solé and Margarita Manzano (MN Consultors); Xavier Romero and Javier Fornieles (Granollers City Council); Miquel Rafa and Josep Maria Fabra (Fundació Catalunya La Pedrera); Oscar Niñerola (Enghydra); Andreu Salvat (Aprèn); Miquel Segarra and Laura Ros (Forestal Catalana); Jordi Vayreda (CREAF – Centre for Ecological Research and Forestry Applications); Quim Bach, Sara Pont and Francesc Diego (Natural Environment Planning Service, Government of Catalonia).

Design and layout:

© of the edition: Forest Science and Technology Centre of Catalonia (CTFC)
© of the texts and illustrations: the authors

First edition: December 2022

Legal deposit: L 417-2023

ISBN: 978-84-09-51245-4

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7997523>

Credits for the photographs: the authors

Credits for the illustrations: ICRA-ART, Pere Rovira, Anthesis Lavola.

Maps: MN Consultors

Front cover photograph: alder forest on the alluvial plain of the Segre River, Cerdanya, Catalonia. Author: Jordi Bas.

The opinions expressed in this handbook are the personal opinions of the authors. They do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Union and the European Commission, nor those of the institutions to which the authors belong, which means that they cannot be attributed to the said institutions.

1.

HEAD INTO THE FOREST

Close-up of flowers and fruits of the alder (*Alnus glutinosa*) / Photo: Jordi Bas.

1. HEAD INTO THE FOREST

What is the river forest?

Rivers have their own aquatic and riparian vegetation. This riparian vegetation eventually becomes a forest (the river forest), forming a characteristic strip alongside the course of the river. River forests are highly diverse and complex, possessing multiple ecosystem functions. They constitute the transition between the aquatic environment and the terrestrial environment away from the water. Moreover, they are closely associated with the riverbed and the underground water close to the surface (water table). The river and the riparian area influenced by the river are together referred to as the “fluvial area” or “river ecosystem”. This interaction between the water and the forest makes them unique ecosystems.

Riparian vegetation

The depth, abundance and constancy of the water table are decisive factors in the floristic composition of riparian vegetation. On each riverbank, the vegetation is arranged in the form of strips of varying widths, where each community selects its place according to its water needs and its resilience; that is, its capacity to withstand periodic floods.

Alder, grey willow, laurel, poplar, elm, white willow, tamarisk, oleander and chaste tree communities are the main representatives of Catalan riparian vegetation. This extraordinary diversity is the result of the complex orography and climatology typical of the Mediterranean region.

This riparian vegetation basically depends on:

- A wide range of flows.
- Environmental and soil humidity, and the sediments brought by the river.
- The facility for the propagation of seeds and vegetative material.
- Access to the water table and sunlight for the establishment of new individuals.
- The salinity of the water and soil.
- The flow regime of the watercourse (permanent, intermittent or ephemeral).

Profile diagrams of riparian vegetation. Top: potential vegetation of a Mediterranean river (the middle-upper course of the Ter) that is representative of southwestern Europe. Bottom: example of riparian vegetation anthropized by agricultural, livestock and forestry uses, and by the lack of flows. Key: 1) Olive willow (*Salix elaeagnos*) community; 2) Alder (*Alnus glutinosa*) community with purple willow (*Salix purpurea*); 3) White willow (*Salix alba*) community; 4) Elm (*Ulmus minor*) community; 5) Ash (*Fraxinus excelsior* or *Fraxinus angustifolia*) community; 6) Oak (*Quercus pubescens*) community; 7) Community of sub-spontaneous necklace poplar (*Populus deltoides*) and London plane (*Platanus x hispanica*) trees; 8) Poplar plantation with bramble undergrowth; 9) Communities of sub-spontaneous invasive woody species – black locust (*Robinia pseudoacacia*) and tree-of-heaven (*Ailanthus altissima*); 10) Grazing and crop land with oaks. Illustrations: Pere Rovira.

White Willow (*Salix alba*)
/ Photo: Shutterstock

Grey willow (*Salix atrocinerea*)
/ Photo: Shutterstock

Silver poplar (*Populus alba*)
/ Photo: Shutterstock

Alder (*Alnus glutinosa*)
/ Photo: Jordi Bas

Elm (*Ulmus minor*)
/ Photo: Shutterstock

European ash (*Fraxinus excelsior*)
/ Photo: Shutterstock

Olive willow (*Salix elaeagnos*)
/ Photo: Shutterstock

At the same time, an extremely interesting interaction is established between the terrestrial and aquatic environments. The submerged parts of the riparian forest (roots, stems, branches) offer shelter to fish, amphibians, aquatic invertebrates and mammals, while the presence of winged insects associated with water attracts birds and insectivorous mammals from all around.

Alder forests

The alder (*Alnus glutinosa*) gives its name to the most complex of the riparian plant communities. The tree grows in flooded or waterlogged soils, which is why it relies on river courses, ponds and wetlands. Its roots tolerate flooding and it has the ability to fix atmospheric nitrogen. While it is the most abundant tree species in this type of forest, it is accompanied by other species, such as the white willow, the European ash, the narrow-leaved ash, the small-leaved lime, the large-leaved lime, the poplar and the elm. Each species tolerates a certain degree of humidity and intermittent flooding. For example, willows (whether in tree or shrub form) can grow on pebbles. One of their adaptive features is that their flexible young stems and branches do not offer resistance to the water current, which prevents them from snapping in floods. With maturity, however, they undergo significant lignification. As a result of these different adaptations and tolerances, the riparian forest arranges itself in three main strips. The strip closest to the river, within the riverbed area itself, among the pebbles and gravel, where the water seeps through, is the willow community. It is mainly formed by plants of the Salicaceae family (such as white willows, olive willows and grey willows), along with some regenerated alders, mostly of the shrub type. Meanwhile, the second strip is the alder community, dominated by alder trees, arranged along the riverbank and in flooded pits. Finally, the third strip is the poplar, silver poplar, ash or elm community, containing vegetation that requires moisture but not flooding.

Alder forests are the main riparian forests in the mountainous areas of wet Catalonia and across the north of the Iberian Peninsula. They appear from sea level up to an altitude of 1700 metres. Catalonia is home to the largest diversity of alder forests in the European Union. Thanks to the presence of these forests and its other riparian habitats, Catalonia can be considered a “sampler” of the ecological mosaic of riparian forests in Western Europe.

Proposed classification of ecological types of alder forest in Catalonia, drawn up by LIFE ALNUS. Source: MN Consultors.

Flooded alder forest alongside the Segre River in the Cerdanya county. One of the finest remaining examples of this habitat on an alluvial plain of the Iberian Peninsula / Photo: Jordi Bas.

What biodiversity is hosted by the river forest?

River ecosystems are among the most diverse on Earth in terms of the variety of species that inhabit them, and riparian forests are the most diverse of European forests. The life they host ranges from microscopic beings, such as algae and bacteria, which cover the surface of river pebbles, to mosses, fungi, aquatic and riparian plants, sponges, nematodes, annelids, molluscs, arthropods, fish, amphibians, reptiles, birds and mammals. All these organisms interact with each other, forming complex trophic networks between the water and land.

Absolute number of bird species and average abundance (mean Ab) by census per point count plot in different types of forest. The total number of bird species in the riparian forests in the point counts is clearly higher than the rest of the surrounding forests. The number of individuals per plot, on the contrary, is not very different. Source for the non-riparian data: Camprodon, J. 2013. *Ecology and Conservation of Forest Birds*. CTFC/Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock and Fishing (DARP)-Government of Catalonia.

Wed vegetation typical of the second line of the riparian forest. The elder (*Sambucus nigra*), in flower, stands out. Ter River in Torelló (Osona county) / Photo: Jordi Bas.

Riparian flora

Up to 426 vascular plants have been determined in the inventories of the LIFE ALNUS project in the Besòs, Ter and Segre basins, with 15.5% of non-native species. These include a threatened species of rush (*Scirpus sylvaticus*) in the Segre basin and seven rare species. The conservation status of the flora in these basins is reasonably good. It decreases in fragmented and grazed forests (wet, nitrophilous grasslands and meadows trampled by cattle), where nitrophilous plants proliferate.

The quality of the riparian vegetation has been determined through the Fluvial Vegetation Index (FVI). Described in the HIDRI protocol of the Catalan Water Agency, which has been drawn up for the assessment of the hydromorphological quality of rivers (Munné et al., 2006), this index assesses the state of conservation of riverbanks by using riparian vegetation as a bioindicator of their naturalness.

Snowdrop (*Galanthus nivalis*), one of the first bulbs to bloom in alder and ash forests, before the trees come into leaf. Ter River in Masies de Voltregà /Photo: Jordi Camprodon.

Riparian and freshwater fauna

In the river ecosystem there are animals that live exclusively in water, such as aquatic macroinvertebrates and fish. Some of the former, such as dragonflies and mayflies, have a two-stage life cycle: larval (aquatic) and adult (aerial). Macroinvertebrates are excellent bioindicators of the state of health of the river; the most sensitive species, such as caddisflies, mayflies and stoneflies, disappear in degraded stretches.

Dragonfly nymph, Coenagrionidae family (*Coenagrion puella*) / Photo: Shutterstock

Adult common backswimmer, Notonectidae family (*Notonecta glauca*) / Photo: Shutterstock

Mayfly nymph, Caenidae family (*Caenis luctuosa*) / Photo: Daan Drukker - observation.org

Diptera larva, black fly or Simuliidae family (*Simulium* sp.) / Photo: shetlandlochs.com

Caddisfly larva, Sericostomatidae family (*Sericostoma personatum*) / Photo: N Sloth - eol.org

Adult common water-measurer, Hydrometridae family (*Hydrometra stagnorum*) / Photo: Shutterstock

Adult riffle beetle, Elmidae family (*Elmis* sp.) / Photo: Cédric Alonso

Eel (*Anguilla anguilla*) / Photo: CERM

Mediterranean barbel (*Barbus meridionalis*) / Photo: Núria Sellarès-CERM

Catalan chub (*Squalius laietanus*) / Photo: Èlia Bretxa-CERM

Trout (*Salmo trutta*) / Photo: Jordi Camprodon

Native fish from the middle and upper sections of the Ter river basin.

In Catalonia there are around 32 native fish species that live in continental waters (fresh or brackish). There are also at least 25 established foreign or non-native species. In the same basin, fish are distributed according to their environmental requirements: temperature, water speed, type of substrate, etc. Many of the native fish are in decline and in a delicate state of conservation, such as the eel and mountain barbel. They are all affected, to varying degrees, by problems of water overexploitation, poor connectivity and competition with invasive species.

Native fish from each of the LIFE ALNUS basins. The number and percentage of non-native species are indicated.

Basin	Eel	Mediterranean barbel	Iberian red-fin barbel	Catalan chub	Trout	Alien species	%
High Segre			*		*	3	50
High Ter		*			*	1	33
Middle Ter		*		*	(*)	9	82
Congost	*	*		*		4	57

The censuses of aquatic macroinvertebrates and fish conducted during the project indicate a certain improvement in terms of population (especially that of the mountain barbel) with the application of the environmental flows at the Gallifa hydroelectric power plant (Middle Ter). Storms Leslie (2018) and Glòria (2020) caused a significant drop in the number of macroinvertebrates and fish, which recovered months later.

Rivers and wetlands are home to a unique combination of fauna comprising amphibians, reptiles and mammals. Some species, such as salamanders and toads, depend on the aquatic environment for the growth of their larvae. In the adult stage, they shelter among the roots of riparian trees. Meanwhile, other amphibians, such as newts and frogs, live there all year round. Many species feed there and find suitable environments in which to reproduce: the Iberian pond turtle, the viperine water snake, the Eurasian water shrew, the southwestern water vole, the Pyrenean desman, the Daubenton's bat or the European polecat.

Salamandra (*Salamandra salamandra*)
/ Photo: Shutterstock

Iberian green frog (*Pelophylax perezi*)
/ Photo: Shutterstock

Spiny toad (*Bufo spinosus*)
/ Photo: Shutterstock

Iberian pond turtle (*Mauremys leprosa*)
/ Photo: Shutterstock

Viperine water snake (*Natrix maura*)
/ Photo: Shutterstock

Slow worm (*Anguis fragilis*)
/ Photo: Shutterstock

Eurasian water shrew (*Neomys fodiens*)
/ Photo: Shutterstock

Pyrenean desman (*Galemys pyrenaicus*)
/ Photo: Shutterstock

Southwestern water vole (*Arvicola sapidus*)
/ Photo: Shutterstock

Lesser noctule (*Nyctalus leisleri*)
/ Photo: Shutterstock

European polecat (*Mustela putorius*)
/ Photo: Shutterstock

Eurasian otter (*Lutra lutra*)
/ Photo: Shutterstock

Colony of birds of the Ardeidae family in an alder forest of the middle course of the Ter River. This is one of the most important bird colonies in Catalonia (more than 300 nests of four species). The upper section is occupied by the grey heron (*Ardea cinerea*), the most corpulent species and the first to arrive; the middle section is occupied by the little egret (*Egretta garzetta*) and cattle egret (*Bubulcus ibis*); finally, the black-crowned night heron (*Nycticorax nycticorax*), the last species to arrive, has to make do with nesting in the lower section, making it the species most vulnerable to predators / Photo: Jordi Bas.

As regards vertebrate fauna, birds are the most abundant group in all the natural environments of Catalonia, and its rivers are certainly no exception, hosting a wide variety of species: some visit these sites to feed and some follow the river course as part of their migratory route between the European and African continents. Meanwhile, some species, such as the grey heron, the little egret, the night heron or the cattle egret, nest there, thus indicating the good state of conservation of that part of the forest. The ten most abundant nesting species in the riparian forests of the Besòs, Ter and Segre river basins are, in order of abundance: the Eurasian blackcap, the common nightingale, the Eurasian wren, the great tit, the common blackbird, the short-toed tree creeper, the mallard, the European robin, the Cetti's warbler and the European serin.

Eurasian blackcap (*Sylvia atricapilla*)
/ Photo: Shutterstock

Common nightingale (*Luscinia megarhynchos*)
/ Photo: Shutterstock

Eurasian wren (*Troglodytes troglodytes*)
/ Photo: Shutterstock

Great tit (*Parus major*)
/ Photo: Shutterstock

Common blackbird (*Turdus merula*)
/ Photo: Shutterstock

Short-toed tree creeper (*Certhia brachydactyla*)
/ Photo: Shutterstock

European serin (*Serinus serinus*)
/ Photo: Shutterstock

European robin (*Erithacus rubecula*)
/ Photo: Shutterstock

Cetti's warbler (*Cettia cetti*)
/ Photo: Shutterstock

Mallard (*Anas platyrhynchos*)
/ Photo: Shutterstock

The aquatic fauna depends on the riverbanks and the riparian fauna depends on the water. As such, macroinvertebrates and fish take refuge and reproduce among the roots of the half-submerged alders and the live or dead alder and willow branches that lie on the riverbed. Common moorhens and ducks breed and sleep in the reeds, bulrushes, bramble patches and branches and roots of the trees near the water. The common kingfisher nests on the earthy slopes. The grey heron, the little egret and the cattle egret gather to breed in the alder forests, while the otter and the Pyrenean desman hunt in the water, their riverbank dens well protected by the vegetation.

Multivariate statistical models (GLMM) have been made to determine how different groups of animals prefer or avoid various elements of the habitat. The table below provides a summary, indicating whether the relationship is positive or negative, along with the level of significance: *p<0.05, **p<0.01, *p<0.001. Tree cover (4-16 m): percentage of plant cover, typically wooded, between 4 and 16 m high. Large trees (> 47.5 cm): density of trees greater than 47.5 cm of DBH (trunk diameter) in trees/ha. Undergrowth (1-4 m): percentage of undergrowth cover (shrubs, lianas and small trees) between 1 and 4 m high. Tree diversity: Shannon’s index for tree species. Fluvial nature: absence of infrastructure (breakwaters, locks, bridges), tested only in terrestrial and semi-aquatic carnivores. Landscape diversity: Shannon index in a 500 m buffer. Proximity to anthropogenic covers: distance to built-up areas and main roads. Native predators: abundance of native carnivores (beech marten, common genet, badger and fox). Non-native predators: abundance of non-native carnivores (American mink, domestic cat and dog).**

Selected element of the habitat	Forest birds	Cavity birds ¹	Arboreal bats ²	Bat’s richness	Forest carnivorous ³	Small mammals ⁴
Vegetal cover (4-16 m)		**			*	
Large trees (> 47,5 cm)	**	**	*	*		
Understory (1-4 m)				*	*	
Tree diversity			***	*		
Fluvial naturality						*
Landscape diversity				**		
Anthropic cover proximity	***				***	
Native predators						*
Alien predators						*

■ positive relationship ■ negative relationship

¹ *Sitta europaea*, *Certhia brachydadyla*, tits, ² *Nyctalus leisleri*, *Nyctalus cf. lasiopterus*, *Myotis crypticus*, *Barbastella barbastellus*. ³ *Genetta genetta*, *Martes foina*, *Meles meles*. ⁴ *Arvicola sapidus*, *Neomys* sp.

Three plant communities in a pond of the Segre River: bulrush or cattail, wet grassland and alder forest / Photo: Jordi Bas.

2.

FUNCTIONS OF THE RIVER FOREST

Riparian forest at the Gallissà Ponds site (Bellver de Cerdanya, Segre River)
/ Photo: Jordi Bas.

2. FUNCTIONS OF THE RIVER FOREST

One of the ecological challenges addressed at the end of the 20th century was to substantially improve river water quality through the sanitation of urban and industrial wastewater. Now, in the second decade of the 21st century, other significant challenges must be met: the facilitation of ecological flows, the minimisation of diffuse pollution, the deurbanization of alluvial plains, and the natural regeneration of fluvial and riparian habitats. Public awareness is key to speeding up the restoration of fluvial areas, just as it has been in restoring water quality. However, the restoration of riparian ecosystems is still a major pending issue. The memory of what great riparian forests must have been like has been lost in the fog of time. We would probably have to go back to before the expansion of agriculture during the Iron Age, if not earlier, in the most populated valleys.

The new paradigm for the planning of alluvial plains

The riparian forest remains misunderstood. The notion persists that fluvial systems and, in particular, riparian vegetation (whether living or dead) constitute a major risk factor for infrastructure in the event of flooding. The standard technical argument is that in order to mitigate the risk of flooding, it is necessary to adapt the river, by means of hydraulic containment works and the reduction of living and/or dead vegetation. Meanwhile, certain customs persist, such as widespread logging to obtain wood and firewood from the riparian forest. Fortunately for the fluvial system, the extraction of sediments from riverbanks to be used as construction material (aggregates) is no longer allowed. The new paradigm proposes changing this perception of risk and shifting away from intensive exploitation towards an ecosystem approach. Installing a rip-rap or earthen berm as a response to the flooding of fields, a campsite or an industrial estate means transferring the problem further downstream where no hydraulic corrective measures are in place. Removing fallen trees due to the risk of them blocking a bridge, or cutting down

an alder forest, means losing ecological functions and ecosystem services. If a bridge is supposedly at risk from the material carried by a flood, it is because this bridge is not suitably adapted to the river that it crosses.

The likelihood of a major flood may be low (on average, they occur every 100 or 500 years or so, depending on the intensity), but there might be one tomorrow. If we look at the location of ancient towns and cities, we can see that they were built near enough to the river to obtain a water supply but far enough away to avoid the inconvenience of flooding. As the Catalan saying goes, “*A la vora del riu no t’hi facis el niu*” (“Next to the river, you’d best not build your nest.”).

The process of urban expansion beyond the confines of the historical centres of towns and cities in the 18th and 19th centuries entailed the construction of homes and factories on the alluvial plain. The consequences of this process were the terrible effects of the great floods, which we are reminded of by memorial plaques and monuments. The subsequent construction of industrial estates, second homes and campsites has further compounded the problem. To reduce the risk of flooding, stretches of river have been canalised or contained by means of rip-raps, completely altering their natural dynamics. While these defences might hold back an ordinary flood, they would end up being overwhelmed in the event of a major flood.

When the flows are extraordinarily high, they collide with the retaining walls, the water gains even more momentum and the risk is transferred to infrastructure elements further downstream. Agricultural, industrial and built-up areas that lack retaining structures receive a greater impact from the flood than they would have if the river had not been contained further upstream.

Does this mean that the river should be canalised all the way to the sea? Or, conversely, should we consider dismantling these defences as far as possible? Freeing up the alluvial plain from walls and built-up areas means that the flow can spread out across the width and length of the plain, thus retaining the transported sediments and, consequently, the circulating water volume. At the same time, it allows water to seep into the water table, and from there into wells and springs, fertilising the plain with the sediments it has brought. Bridges and other infrastructure elements can be remodelled and built in such a way that they no longer constitute a flood risk. Roman and mediaeval bridges that were built with this principle in mind have survived to this day. Are we not able to achieve this today? So far we have tried to tame the river without much success. With the climate crisis hanging over us like Damocles’ sword, and as part of the transition to a more sustainable model of environmental and human growth, perhaps it is time to adapt to change and free our rivers.

Mediaeval bridge over the Ges River (Ter river basin in Osona). This is an example of a construction adapted to the flooding of the river. Its wide arch allows the drainage of floods, which is how it has survived intact to this day / Photo: Jordi Camprodon.

In light of these precedents and the challenges we face, we must consider the essential ecosystem functions provided by riparian forests, integrated within the fluvial area as a whole, defining and regulating the ecology of rivers.

Scenic value

The singular, extraordinary beauty of riparian vegetation is well known. It is a key component of the landscape, associated since ancient times with quiet contemplation, walks, gatherings around springs and fishing, along with all sorts of artistic expressions. The splendour of riparian vegetation has been exalted throughout the history of art. Riparian forests add great scenic and economic value to the area, offering plenty of potential for recreational and ecotourism activities.

Effects of riparian vegetation on floods

Riparian vegetation is an effective tool for managing river floods, since it helps to retain the flow of water and to reduce its speed. Flood plains, and the forest that naturally occupies them, are nature's flood control solution.

During floods, the river forest reduces the speed of the water and retains sediments and floating material. However, if the river is canalised and its surroundings are turned into built-up areas, it flows faster and causes more damage when it overflows. The sediment and organic remains brought by a flood increase soil fertility.

Great egret (*Casmerodius albus*) taking flight from the Ter River in the autumn / Photo: Jordi Bas.

Typical species of Catalan rivers. 1. Common kingfisher (*Alcedo atthis*). 2. Grey wagtail (*Motacilla cinerea*). 3. Mediterranean barbel (*Barbus meridionalis*). 4. Adult trout and fry (*Salmo trutta*). 5. Eel (*Anguilla anguilla*). 6. White-clawed crayfish (*Austropotamobius pallipes*). 6. Water strider (*Gerris* sp.). 6. Black-tailed skimmer (*Orthetrum cancellatum*). 9. Alder with submerged roots (*Alnus glutinosa*). 10. Snowdrop (*Galanthus nivalis*). 11. Elder (*Sambucus nigra*). 12. Common reed (*Phragmites australis*). 13. Roundhead bulrush (*Scirpus holoschoenus*). Illustration: ICRA-ART.

Shelter for animals and plants

Fluvial areas are among the most complex and biodiverse ecosystems on Earth. They contribute decisively to preserving genetic diversity. Their function as biological corridors facilitates the genetic exchange between distant populations.

River altered by the occupation of riverbanks, direct pollution (domestic and industrial sources) and diffuse pollution (agricultural sources). Illustration: ICRA-ART

Pollution filter

Riparian forests improve water quality and transparency, filtering suspended sediments and absorbing nutrients from human activities (industrial, agricultural and urban). The microorganisms they contain purify diffuse pollution, such as that of slurry, and a certain proportion of wastewater.

Regulation of the degree of insolation and water temperature

The vegetation and the percentage of tree cover on the riverbank serve to regulate the temperature of the water and the degree of insolation on the riverbed. The more shade there is on the riverbed, the more stable and cooler the temperature of the river water, and the greater the diversity of plants and animals in the ecosystem.

Aquatic (or semi-aquatic) species typical of Catalan rivers. 1. Mallard (*Anas platyrhynchos*). 2. Southwestern water vole (*Arvicola sapidus*). 3. Otter (*Lutra lutra*). 4. Black-crowned night heron (*Nycticorax nycticorax*). 5. Grey heron (*Ardea cinerea*). 6. Little egret (*Egretta garzetta*). 7. Silver poplar (*Populus alba*). 8. Snowdrop (*Galanthus nivalis*). 9. Broadleaf cattail (*Thypha latifolia*) and alder (*Alnus glutinosa*). 10. Common reed (*Phragmites australis*). Illustration: ICRA-ART.

The rivers are like highways that facilitate the movement of plants and animals along and across the basin and between basins. The riparian forest, at the same time, allows forest fauna to connect between large areas of forest separated by agricultural plains. River Ter on its way through the Plana de Vic plain to the North of Barcelona / Photo: Jordi Bas.

Connectivity

The aquatic environment and the riparian forest are first-rate biological corridors, a fast track for the movements of fauna and the dispersal of plant propagules. For example, bird migration takes place to a large extent following river courses and valleys. Fluvial areas make it possible to connect populations from different territories and basins, for example between the Besòs, Upper Ter and Upper Segre basins. This is the case with aquatic and semi-aquatic birds and mammals such as ducks, the grey heron, the Daubenton's bat and the otter. Where the demolition of dams and locks is not possible, fish passage devices provide upstream passage through dams and locks, facilitating the reproduction and dispersal of fish populations along the entire fluvial network.

Ramp for fish in the Teula lock (Ter River in Manlleu, Osona county) / Photo: marc Ordeix.

3.

THE ALTERATION OF THE NATURAL STATE OF THE RIVER FOREST

Restoration of the transportation of sediments and of lateral flooding through the removal of the canalisation structure and of an obsolete lock (Congost River in Granollers, Besòs basin) / Photo: Aprèn Serveis Ambientals.

Human activity in fluvial areas, such as aggregate extraction, uncontrolled dumping of industrial substances, pipelines, power generation, agricultural and livestock uses, etc., has generated a series of pressures on river ecosystems that persist today, causing highly modified basins and serious problems for the survival of these habitats. 1. Water pollution, 2. Water catchments and lack of ecological flows, 3. Degradation of riparian vegetation, 4. Alien species, 5. Lack of ecological connectivity. Illustration: ICRA-ART.

3. THE ALTERATION OF THE NATURAL STATE OF THE RIVER FOREST

Rivers have always provided humans with invaluable resources. Since ancient times, river ecosystems have been greatly influenced by human activity: riparian vegetation was intensively used on the alluvial plains, ending up being replaced by crops and pastures in many places. With the onset of the Industrial Revolution, river courses were greatly modified by locks, canals and the progressive urban development of their banks, so much so that most riparian forests on the plains and in the valleys are in an extremely poor state of conservation or have simply disappeared. Despite the efforts made to preserve and improve them, the fluvial areas of plains and valleys that have been greatly impacted by human activity are far from being in good ecological condition. In fact, riparian forests covering extensive areas of alluvial plains have become practically extinct landscapes on the Iberian Peninsula. There are many reasons for their disappearance, of which the main ones are briefly described below.

1-The transformation of river ecosystems

Thanks to their flat, extremely fertile land and their water resources, river valleys and plains have long been occupied and heavily exploited by humans. Floodplains have largely or mostly been used for agriculture, livestock farming, sediment extraction, urban development, infrastructure construction and intensive forestry. This degradation entails soil erosion and loss, along with increased pollution, given that plants retain the soil and at the same time act as pollutant filters. The transformation of alluvial plains has meant the reduction or loss of a unique, extremely rich biological heritage. Moreover, when they are turned into built-up areas, their enormous potential to supply local food is lost.

The monitoring of biological indicators by the LIFE ALNUS project has provided valuable data to help us understand the distribution of bioindicator organisms in relation to the state of conservation of the riparian forest and the aquatic environment associated with the landscape matrix. River stretches with more extensive and complex riparian forests (with greater plant diversity and maturity) contain greater biodiversity, especially landscapes with an agroforestry mosaic or those dominated by zonal forests.

2-Contamination of water

Surface and groundwater pollution comes largely from discharges of industrial, agricultural, livestock and domestic origin. Although the sanitation systems implemented in Catalonia and the rest of the European Union make it possible to regulate most or much of urban and industrial wastewater, there is still a significant amount of diffuse pollution, associated with agricultural and livestock activities, which gradually filters into surface and groundwater.

Fluvial areas have the ability to self-purify, to break down the organic matter that reaches them naturally; that is, the matter which forms part of the same ecological system (leaves, trunks, etc.). They can also absorb some of the organic and nutrient load that comes from human activities. However, self-purification depends on the intensity, the flow of each river course and the type of discharge. All too often, the assimilation capacity of the river and the riparian vegetation is exceeded. We were able to observe this phenomenon during the monitoring of biological indicators (aquatic macroinvertebrates and fish) carried out as part of the LIFE ALNUS project. For example, when an urban wastewater collector broke down for a few days in September 2020, the biological quality of a stretch of the Ter River in the Ripollès area, which had begun to recover with the application of an environmental flow regime, became simplified.

3-Water extraction and flow variation

In Mediterranean rivers, the density of uses for irrigation or for the production of electricity is particularly high. Agriculture, for example, uses around three quarters of the water consumed in Catalonia. The remaining water consumption is divided between livestock, industry and domestic use.

The extraction of water from rivers means that flows are lower than desired, creating a water deficit, an extraordinary contribution of nutrients and water stress on riparian vegetation. The lack of flows downstream from dams and locks hampers the survival and regeneration of the alder and other riparian woody species, whose roots must always be kept moist or soaked. LIFE ALNUS has reached agreements with a hydroelectric company to release more water during droughts in the stretches downstream from two locks on the Ter River, and to monitor the improvement of the river ecosystem.

4-Lack of maturity of the river forest

There are almost no mature riparian forests left; that is, forests with trees of different ages, including old trees and abundant dead wood. To a certain extent, floods serve to rejuvenate riparian forests more frequently than fires or other natural disturbances serve to renew non-riparian forests. Conversely, the widespread coppicing of alder forests does not favour them. This practice consists of felling all the trees in a stand once they reach a certain age (for example, 25 years in the case of the alder) or a certain diameter.

Although it is not a particularly long-lived tree, the alder can live for over 100 years. As such, the coppicing management model means that the trees cannot reach maturity. Meanwhile, dead wood is usually removed for fear of damage to bridges, locks and canals, especially after floods. LIFE ALNUS proposes a nature-based model for the management of riparian forests where there is an interest in producing commercial wood. The nature-based management model imitates natural processes, ensuring continuous cover in order to facilitate progress towards greater complexity and maturity, to host a wide variety of biodiversity, and to fulfil the joint ecological functions of the forest and the river. After flooding, LIFE ALNUS proposes leaving much of the dead wood in place. Furthermore, it advises against chopping it up, since by leaving it intact it is more difficult for the river to take it downstream. In forests where wood is not extracted, all that is required is to allow them to grow and age freely.

Dead wood well integrated in the soil, the result of a natural forest ageing process. The clearing created by the fall of older trees is an opportunity for the growth of the seedlings of new plants. This is a natural, continuous regeneration (or renewal) process of the forest. Alder Forest alongside the Segre River in Cerdanya county / Photo: Jordi Bas.

5-Invasive species

Invasive species are introduced, non-native or exotic species that become established in a territory which is not their native habitat and which they have entered due to human action. It is estimated that approximately 10-20% of the species that arrive in our territory have the ability to adapt to it. Among naturalised species, a further 10-20% have a great capacity for resistance and proliferation. Their adaptability allows them to propagate throughout natural environments, competing with and displacing native species, modifying ecosystems, and affecting the local economy and even human health.

Fluvial areas are the ecosystems in which invasive species, such as the red swamp crayfish (an aquatic species) and the American mink (a semi-aquatic species) can spread most easily. The indigenous riparian vegetation competes with species with a great capacity for propagation, such as species of the *Robinia* genus, trees-of-heaven, box elders and reeds. Previous studies by the LIFE ALNUS project have mapped and demonstrated the expansion of invasive plant species in all three project basins. The strategy for strengthening native riparian vegetation has consisted of identifying and acting in river stretches where invasive species were present but not dominant.

6-Lack of ecological connectivity

The aforementioned environmental impacts fragment riparian habitats. Apart from the headwaters of mountain streams, the continuity of riparian forests has been lost in valleys and alluvial plains, often after centuries of human occupation of these areas. The presence of hydraulic facilities and the lack of flows hinder or prevent the movement and connectivity of wildlife populations. One affected species is the eel, which has already disappeared from inland Catalonia. However, all native fish populations have been affected and are in decline everywhere, among other reasons due to the severe difficulty they encounter in accessing their spawning or feeding sites. The LIFE ALNUS restoration actions are aimed at reducing the fragmentation of the riparian forest.

7-Effects of climate change

Mediterranean fluvial areas are particularly vulnerable to climate change. The ordinary flows of watercourses can suddenly fall and rise due to the progressive increase in temperature, the reduction in rainfall and the increasing recurrence of extraordinary episodes of drought and flooding. These climatic conditions are already showing an effect on the riparian communities and, in particular, on alder forests.

The LIFE ALNUS project has been able to verify how the decline observed in alders at the head of basins is related to severe recurring droughts. Alder roots must always be wet or even flooded, which is why the tree is particularly sensitive to the lack of surface or underground flows. If the roots spend too much time with low humidity, the tree decays and eventually dies. It is likely that the progressive and natural reforestation of headwaters from the second half of the 20th century has reduced flows in watercourses due to an increase in evapotranspiration. This would explain why the alders at the head of the basin are the ones that tend to decay, apparently without human intervention. At the current rate of climate change, this decline will probably increase. If climate change intensifies, the alder is likely to disappear in some stretches and its place may be taken by more drought-tolerant species, such as willows and ashes.

Alder forest in decline, with dead and dying alder trees caused by droughts, in the Besòs basin / Photo: Jordi Camprodon.

The alder adapts to the flow changes of rivers modified by hydrological facilities, thriving upstream from locks but declining immediately downstream from them. Alders can also disappear when the water level drops due to modifications of the river channel or as a result of the extraction of sediments for the construction sector (aggregates).

The effect of extraordinary floods (storms Leslie and Glòria) has also been shown. The transfer and sedimentation of silts, gravels and pebbles has altered the river landscape and temporarily modified the macroinvertebrate and fish communities. A large number of trees that had been growing for a long period (since the 1980s) during which there had been no flooding on this scale, were uprooted and fell. The falling of trees is a natural process. However, the establishment of more mature high forests can reduce the mass falling of trees. The adaptation of infrastructure elements (for example, bridges) to cope with floods and the freeing up of floodplains would minimise the effects of flooding on goods and services.

Models to predict the vulnerability of alder forests to climate change in Catalonia in the short term and in the long term. Source: MN Consultors.

8-Insufficient legal protection and complex governance

Unfortunately, the best examples of alder forest in many cases do not enjoy proper legal protection. Despite the great effort made in deploying the Natura 2000 Network, few fluvial areas in Catalonia are protected by it. The LIFE ALNUS project has found that some of the best examples of alder forest on the alluvial plain (extremely sparse) are outside the area of protection of the Special Areas of Conservation (SACs), which is why one of the main actions proposed by the project is to extend this legal protection.

Meanwhile, fluvial areas bring together a wide range of socioeconomic interests: primary, industrial and service sector activities, drinking water supply and other ecosystem services, urban expansion, recreational activities, interest in their protection and recovery, etc. These interests and factors interact with each other, making fluvial areas perhaps the most complex natural systems of all in terms of governance. It is not surprising that there is often a lack of coordination between the sectors involved, between protection measures at the European, state and Catalan level, between the different administrative bodies and between these bodies and citizens. Consequently, a review of the existing protection measures (mainly the Natura 2000 Network) and governance models is clearly necessary.

The Iberian problem is therefore paradigmatic, especially in Catalonia: it is probably one of the European biogeographical regions with the greatest potential for improving the conservation status of its habitat, but at the same time it faces some of the most difficult conservation challenges. This means that the experiences acquired through the LIFE ALNUS project and other similar ones will serve as valuable models for future action.

Nature 2000 network

PWD

PFA

Example of alluvial plain with a potentially fluvial area (PFA, area flooded by the river in extraordinary floods), the Public Water Domain (PWD) and the area included in the Natura 2000 Network. As can be observed, the PWD and PFA cover areas that have been transformed to varying degrees by agricultural and livestock farming activity. These are areas with the potential to be turned into riparian habitats, subject to agreements with landowners (public or private) and with the administrative body of the basin. The Natura 2000 Network could be extended to the restored areas. Source: MN Consultors/ICGC.

9- Pèrdua de biodiversitat

Inland aquatic habitats occupy just 3% of Catalonia's surface area, but they host more than 30% of its threatened species and are the habitats that have suffered the greatest loss of biodiversity in the last 20 years.

Population trends for different types of environments. Based on the Living Planet Index (LPI) is a measure of the state of global biological diversity. When applied to the habitats of Catalonia, it indicates that aquatic habitats have been in steep decline over the last two decades. Source: Observatory of Natural Heritage and Biodiversity of Catalonia (OPNB) (2020).

Vallforners creek near the Oms Spring, in Cardedeu, (Vallès Oriental county), Besòs basin / Photo: Jordi Bas.

4.

THE LIFE ALNUS PROJECT

The Segre River in Cerdanya county is one of the best examples in Catalonia of a river free of artificial obstacles / Photo: Jordi Bas.

4. THE LIFE ALNUS PROJECT

LIFE ALNUS is a project for the conservation, restoration and governance of alder forests and other related riparian forests, such as willow, poplar, ash and elm forests, or mixed forests of alders, willows, ashes, elms and poplars. It is co-funded by the LIFE Nature and Biodiversity Programme of the European Union, which includes the improvement of habitats and species of the Natura 2000 Network.

The Natura 2000 Network protects the most important natural areas in the European Union. These areas contain habitats and species of flora and fauna of community importance due to their precarious state of conservation.

LIFE ALNUS river basins with the current and potential distribution of riparian vegetation. Source: MN Consultors.

The purpose of the project

The conservation of riparian forests poses a major scientific, social and political challenge for Europe which, to date, has only been addressed through one-off, local restoration projects. In other words, there has not yet been a European project with an integrated, cross-cutting approach to the conservation of riparian forests at a regional or national scale. This situation would not be serious if the evolution of the riparian forest habitat were positive after 30 years of the Habitats Directive. However, this is not the case: for the European Mediterranean region as a whole, the conservation status of riparian forests has shifted from inadequate to bad between 2007 and 2018, according to the European Commission.

This is the challenge facing LIFE ALNUS. The project has been implemented in three pilot basins (Besòs, Ter and Segre), covering more than 1,000 linear kilometres. The three basins encompass more than 50.5% of the geographical distribution of Catalonia's alder forests. It should be highlighted that the Spanish section of the Natura 2000 Network contains 48% of the surface area of alder forests in the Mediterranean region. This means that Spain (and, in turn, Catalonia, with almost 15% of the aforementioned surface area) bears a significant amount of responsibility for the conservation of this habitat in Mediterranean Europe.

Catalonia is home to a great diversity of riparian forests, from headwater alder forests to willow, poplar and alder forests on alluvial plains. The great valleys and plains are precisely where these habitats are most degraded and fragmented, to such an extent that it is estimated that more than 80% of the riparian forests of the European alluvial plains have been lost. Due to their critical conservation status throughout Europe, alder forests and other riparian forests have been classified as habitats of community importance in the Habitats Directive of the European Union.

Catalonia is probably one of the European biogeographical regions with the greatest potential for improving the conservation status of its habitat, but at the same time it faces some of the most difficult conservation challenges, which means that the experience acquired through this project, transferable to other basins, serves as a valuable example of what can be done. Moreover, Catalonia forms part of the Mediterranean front where alder forests will have to adapt to more intense and recurring periods of drought as a result of climate change.

Preparatory actions

What was the conservation status of the habitat before the project?

In order to approach the conservation of alder forests strategically at the basin scale, it was necessary to determine the conservation status of the riparian forests in the three ALNUS basins (Segre, Ter and Besòs). From the inception of the project, work was carried out to diagnose and understand the causes of habitat loss, in order to systematically plan where it was most important to act. Since economic and human resources tend to be limited, it was necessary to decide in which river stretches (divided into units of approximately 500 linear metres) conservation or recovery actions could be most efficient:

1. Stretches where the habitat was fragmented and the continuity of the forest could be restored.
2. Stretches where the habitat had disappeared and there was significant potential for its reintroduction.
3. Stretches with underdeveloped vegetation, with many sprouting trees, where silvicultural work could be carried out to improve the vigour and heterogeneity of trees.

4. Stretches with the presence of non-native plant species, especially those of an invasive nature. The selected stretches had to be ones in which these non-native species were not dominant but rather scattered in small groups within communities dominated by native species. This ensured the optimisation of results (low cost/benefit).
5. Stretches and river courses with alder forests and other fluvial habitats of community importance located beyond the Natura 2000 Network. Priority was given to alder forests on the alluvial plain, which are the ones that have disappeared the most since ancient times.

As a whole, they were stretches which together contained a combination of problems, which had not deteriorated excessively and which offered great potential for recovery, ensuring a cost-effective benefit for nature.

More than 1000 river kilometres were analysed between the three basins of the ALNUS project. Only 316 hectares of alder forests were mapped (184 hectares in the Segre, 106 hectares in the Ter and 26 hectares in the Besòs). This figure was much lower than expected on the basis of previous data. In addition, 2043 hectares of riparian forest with the presence of alder and 432 hectares of willow forests and mixed forests without alders were mapped.

Plans for the restoration and conservation of the habitat

Following the diagnosis, riparian forest conservation plans were drawn up for each basin. These plans prioritised stretches in which to intervene on the basis of the diagnosed problems. Interventions in the high-priority stretches were carried out by LIFE ALNUS. Interventions will be carried out in other stretches in the near future, through new projects.

An integrated vision of the restoration of fluvial habitats (understood as the area encompassing the river and the riparian forest) entails the renaturalisation of the dynamics, processes and flows that govern them, as well as removing the hydromorphological or chemical barriers, disconnections and discontinuities that prevent the integrity of the basin continuum from being maintained.

Alder planted during the restoration of the riparian forest on the Congost River (Besòs basin), near Lledoner Park (Granollers, Vallès Oriental county) / Photo: Jordi Bas.

1. Invasive species elimination and control measures	3. Measures to restore the longitudinal continuity of the habitat
2. Forest management measures	4. Habitat reintroduction in courses where it became extinct

Example of the methodology followed to design the strategy of the Habitat Restoration and Conservation Plans for each LIFE ALNUS basin. The conservation action consisted of identifying the best-preserved river stretches or those with the greatest potential for restoration in which to expand the Natura 2000 Network. The restoration was based on four actions: 1) elimination and control of exotic species; 2) improvement of the structure of the riparian forest with silvicultural treatments; 3) defragmentation of the habitat through planting; and 4) reintroduction of the habitat in stretches where it has disappeared. The spatial planning of each action started from the analysis of alternatives: a) by means of suitability or importance indices of each stretch; b) using prioritisation models based on systematic planning (Marxan conservation planning software). The map in the attached figure represents the resulting model for the reintroduction of riparian forest. The stretches that were initially identified for their strategic interest were then studied in more detail through fieldwork and reviewed by the partners responsible for (and knowledgeable about) each basin. The purpose of all this was to make the final selection of the stretches in which to carry out the intervention would take place. Once the stretches were selected, the work was carried out on the ground: homogenous surfaces (stands) were distinguished where actions were planned, the vegetation was inventoried and the possibilities of intervention were analysed based on their ecological characteristics and other social-legal aspects. Source: MN Consultors / CTFC.

Agreements with landowners

In order to protect, improve and conserve riparian forests, it was necessary to reach so-called river stewardship agreements with various types of landowner: individuals, companies, public authorities, etc.

Over the course of the project, agreements have been reached with 17 private landowners and three public landowners, including a hydroelectric company.

Signing of a river stewardship agreement with the owner of the Can Batista estate (Ter basin, Torelló) in 2021, as part of the LIFE ALNUS project / Photo: Marc Ordeix.

Conservation actions

The project was based on the premise that the best option for the restoration of fluvial areas is the recovery of natural dynamics; that is, enabling the river to regulate itself through the recovery of flows and the dynamics of sediments and the flooding regime. This passive restoration strategy can be implemented when the impact factors have disappeared or decreased significantly. However, this is not always possible. Therefore, the ultimate goal of the project is to implement active restoration actions that facilitate the recovery of natural processes, thus enabling the river to organise itself. Accordingly, the fluvial system is improved through the removal of dams and barriers, the restoration of flows and the elimination of invasive species, while the structure of the forest is improved through silvicultural work and planting.

Improved protection of riparian forests

The LIFE ALNUS project completes the Catalan strategy for the conservation of riparian forests by strengthening the improvement and expansion of the Natura 2000 Network. Despite the great effort that has been made in Catalonia to cover 31% of the territory within the Natura 2000 Network, there were still river courses and/or alder forests and other riparian habitats of community importance in the ALNUS basins that were underrepresented and outside the legal protection area of the Natura 2000 Network. Accordingly, the project worked in close collaboration with the Directorate General for Environmental Policies and the Natural Environment (DGPA) of the Government of Catalonia, which is the body responsible for planning the Natura 2000 Network in Catalonia.

The selection of areas began during the preparatory actions and ended with the administrative procedures initiated by the DGPA. An innovative component of the action was the participatory process carried out with the competent public authorities and the territorial and social stakeholders. The purpose was to achieve as great a consensus as possible with the local population. As a final result, plans have been put in place to extend the Natura 2000 Network to the fluvial areas of the Segre, Ter and Besòs basins by around 600 hectares.

- 1 Segre River stretch
- 2 Ter River and Freser River stretch
- 3 Ter Meanders stretch
- 4 Major Stream and Espinelves Stream stretch
- 5 Cànoves Stream stretch

Location map of the fluvial-riparian areas included in the proposal for the extension of the Natura 2000 Network. Source: Natural Environment Planning Service, Government of Catalonia.

Restoration of riparian vegetation

In the case of riparian forests, it is important to recover the lost continuity of the habitat, since this continuity makes it possible to foster ecological connectivity. LIFE ALNUS has implemented actions to restore deteriorated sections of the riparian forest that still offer optimal potential for recovery. These sections have been identified as priority areas in the conservation plans. The actions have focused on four aspects:

1. The reconnection of the fluvial continuum (defragmentation of the habitat).
2. The reintroduction of the habitat in sub-basins and extensive stretches in which it has disappeared.
3. The control of exotic species.
4. The improvement of the complexity of the structure of the forest, along with its maturity and biodiversity.

The reconnection and reintroduction of the habitat was carried out by means of the planting of indigenous woody species, in the form of seedlings or starter plants (using stakes), gathered from the basin itself. The control of exotic species was carried out using the best possible practices, prioritising the felling and tree injection of invasive vegetation in places where native woody vegetation could easily reclaim and cover the area. Good forest management practices were applied, consisting of the selection of shoots, selective felling, the production of dead wood by ringing or felling trees, where it was in short supply. Hydromorphological restoration work was occasionally carried out to recover old river branches that had disappeared. Finally, the remains from felling were used to build otter dens.

Plant production for LIFE ALNUS at the public enterprise Forestal Catalana nursery, in Breda (Vallès Oriental county). Alder seed saplings (like those in the image), European and narrow-leaved ashes, poplar, elder, and dogwood, among others, were obtained. Also white, purple, bitter and grey willows were produced from stakes. The fruits and cuttings were collected in the same basin, from trees and bushes close to where the riparian forest restoration projects were carried out. The aim was for the plantation to be from the same genetic population. Thus, genetic variability was preserved and at the same time, a better adaptation of the plants was achieved / Photo: Jordi Camprodon.

Selected felling in an old plane forest in order to recover the natural riparian vegetation. Certain large plane trees that compete with the ashes, maples and lindens are selected for felling. Other plane trees are left alone because they provide shade for the stream, protect the riverbanks and/or host many threatened species. The black locust trees are all felled because of their invasive nature. Sora Stream (Ter basin), Montesquiu Castle Park / Photo: Jordi Camprodon.

Pilot projects

River ecosystem restoration projects were carried out in each ALNUS basin, comprising innovative actions whose successes and failures would be useful for the design and implementation of future projects in Catalan basins and those of the European Mediterranean region as a whole.

The actions consisted of restoring and facilitating natural dynamics. Within each basin, stretches were selected that contained an adequate representation of the various problems affecting Mediterranean alder forests on alluvial plains. These stretches required innovative, elaborate technical approaches due to a series of complex features, such as deep incisions, a high degree of deterioration or the strong regulation of the hydrological regime.

The pilot projects were as follows:

1) Removal and reduction of barriers, and restoration of the habitat that had disappeared in the built-up stretch of the Congost River (Besòs basin) in the conurbation of Granollers. Reintroduction of the alder forest. 72 ha. / Photo: Jordi Bas.

2) Restoration of the hydromorphological dynamics of sediments and removal of barriers on two river islands of the middle course of the Ter River. Les Gambires and Sorral Islands (Torelló-Masies de Voltregà). 19.2 ha. / Photo: Jordi Camprodon.

3) Restoration of hydromorphological processes and of an alder forest on the alluvial plain of the Segre River. Gallissà Pounds, Segre River, Bellver de Cerdanya. 4.5 ha. / Photo: Jordi Bas.

4) Recovery of flows downstream from two locks used for the hydroelectric exploitation of the Ter River, a highly regulated river in hydromorphological terms. Dams of El Mariner (Camprodon) and Gallifa (Masies de Voltregà), Ter River, managed by the company Estabanell y Pahisa, SA / Photo: Jordi Bas.

Regulating public use

Visiting river sites is a typical recreational activity that should be encouraged. However, we frequently come across situations that make regulation and intervention necessary in order to improve the quality of rivers and streams and their forests. As such, with the help of various groups, hikers, fishing enthusiasts and naturalists, a series of guidelines and recommendations have been drawn up to facilitate a better environmental use of riparian forests.

Sports fishing sites have been determined in agreement with local fishing organisations.

Section of the *Camí vora Ges* (Ges Riverside Path), a project implemented in the 1990s by the Grup de Defensa del Ter (Ter River Protection Group), aimed at enabling the public to rediscover the river / Photo: Jordi Camprodon.

Management guidelines

Over the last few years, during the implementation of the LIFE ALNUS project, several documents have been produced, such as a set of guidelines for the treatment of plant remains after floods. A handbook has been published describing experiences in the conservation and restoration of fluvial areas that can serve as a model for addressing problems related to the conservation of these areas. It includes technical guidelines for the sustainable forest management of riparian forests.

Governance

We aim to raise awareness about the social importance of restoring riparian forests, both as green infrastructures and as sites of important environmental, cultural and experiential values. Furthermore, we aim to inform and raise the awareness of landowners and land managers about new habitat management criteria.

A process for the improvement of governance has been undertaken using an approach based on discussion rooms with different groups. These groups were established in order to discuss and

reach a consensus that reconciles the environmental values, economic activities and social uses of fluvial areas. The discussion rooms hosted managers of natural areas, forestry professionals, hydraulic engineers, owners of rural estates with riparian areas, local councillors, representatives of hydroelectric and extractive companies, naturalist, ecological and/or land stewardship associations, and groups that organise recreational river activities. Each discussion room drew up a list of ten actions to be implemented, agreed upon by all the participants and available to view on the LIFE ALNUS website.

To achieve as much public awareness of the project as possible, various tools have been used, including social networks, a newsletter, an exhibition, environmental education activities, posters, handbooks, etc. All these materials are available on the website: www.lifealnus.eu.

Ecological monitoring

Various hydromorphological indicators (flows, topography, sediments) and biological indicators (aquatic macroinvertebrates, fish, riparian flora and vegetation, riparian birds, and semi-aquatic and riparian mammals) have been monitored. Through an initial extensive sampling process, the association was established between the bioindicators and the complexity of the riparian forest structure. The second goal of monitoring was to evaluate, in the short and long term, the response of the hydromorphological and biological indicators to the habitat improvement and restoration actions. Finally, the results and conclusions, derived both from the previous studies and from the monitoring of bioindicators, have provided basic information to be integrated in the planning of the actions of the LIFE ALNUS project, and in adaptive management plans to enable its replicability in other river basins.

Scientific sampling of fish by means of electric fishing in the Ter River in Les Masies de Voltregà by the team of the Centre for the Study of Mediterranean Rivers – University of Vic – Central University of Catalonia. October 2021 / Photo: Pol Guardis.

5.

CHALLENGES FOR THE FUTURE

Submerged alder roots, a magnificent example of the association between forest and water (Fornès River, Ter basin) / Photo: Jordi Bas.

5. CHALLENGES FOR THE FUTURE

Listed below is a selection of the most important actions proposed by the LIFE ALNUS discussion rooms. They address both the current and future challenges identified by social actors in the management and use of river ecosystems or fluvial areas.

- Implement a more adaptive management of fluvial areas. The recovery of natural dynamics is the solution for reducing flood risks, recovering floodplains and old river branches that help to relieve swelling rivers and reduce the impact of flooding on infrastructure. Incorporate global change scenarios (which predict a significant decrease in circulating flows) in the future dynamics of riparian forests.
- Active ecological restoration must be applied where necessary to recover and monitor natural processes: removal of locks and canals, fish passes, silvicultural actions, regulation of invasive species, hydromorphological and vegetation restoration. Promote the active management of sediments in locks and large reservoirs to facilitate the transportation of solids (pebbles, gravel, sand and mud), considering that both environmental flows and the transportation of sediments are essential for the maintenance of fluvial areas.
- The common goal of managers and users of fluvial areas is to restore the favourable ecological status of the riparian forest for ecosystem services, in compliance with the Habitats Directive and Water Framework Directive of the European Union. Compatibility must be ensured with other goals, such as timber production activities and public use.
- River courses are a strategic green infrastructure. It is necessary to manage their urban planning uses in accordance with their risks and environmental values. The aim should be to move towards removing buildings at high risk of flooding and that have a negative impact on the river.
- Promote river stewardship as a priority instrument for harmonising urban/agricultural management with the conservation of riverbanks and riverbeds. Offer incentives to landowners to extend riparian forest areas. Strike a balance between productive forest management and the presence of ecologically functional riparian forests of greater maturity and biodiversity. Options include fiscal measures, incentives for the adoption of good practices, and the facilitating river stewardship agreements.

Grey heron (*Ardea cinerea*) and cattle egret (*Bubulcus ibis*) nests in a alder forest in the Ter River in Torelló (Osona county) / Photo: Jordi Bas.

- Identify and recover stretches of old-growth riparian forests and in a good state of conservation in order to leave them to their natural dynamics and monitor them. They constitute highly functional and diverse benchmark systems for scientific monitoring and the application of management measures in multifunctional stretches.
- Increase knowledge (through pilot tests) of various fluvial area management measures in relation to their risks (sediments, timber drift, flooding) and the environmental services they provide. Furthermore, assess the implications of the good management of river functionality and of plant communities in reducing the risk of floods, establishing forest areas with different types of intervention in order to make the different uses compatible and with the goal of minimising the risks for infrastructure elements.
- Reach a consensus on easily applicable, crosscutting management guidelines for riparian forests. The guidelines must be related to the recovery of the functionality of riparian forests and biodiversity, to the strengthening of the resilience of riparian systems in the face of climate change and, therefore, to the regulation and minimisation of the risks associated with flooding.
- Undertake a study on the carrying capacity of riparian ecosystems in respect of different change factors, such as the degree of human presence in fluvial areas. The capacity should be calculated at a basin scale and local (municipal) scale, considering the specific characteristics of each stretch, suitable times of year for recreational activities and the periods of fragility for flora and fauna.
- Promote Basin Councils as entities that can foster collaborative work and the transfer and exchange of information on the management of fluvial areas between all the stakeholders.
- Draw up a training and dissemination plan for the management of fluvial areas aimed at politicians, technicians of public authorities, companies and organisations. The plan must include concepts such as riparian forest ecosystem services, tools to strike a balance between the environmental risks related to emergency events and the environmental benefits that high-quality riparian areas provide.
- Update public policies and legislation on the basis of all the new knowledge that is being generated related to a more integrated vision of fluvial dynamics.
- Launch citizen awareness campaigns to explain the importance of urban fluvial areas and the environmental benefits associated with the conservation of their natural values, especially the recovery of riparian forests. Involve citizens in the monitoring of projects carried out in fluvial areas through citizen science initiatives.
- Carry out long-term monitoring of restoration projects. Provide the financial resources to make them effective. Select pilot stretches to generate simple, small-scale hydrological and vegetation growth models, in order to facilitate understanding of the ecological dynamics of the riparian forest (regeneration, growth, maturity and decay) and of the associated biodiversity.

Elements to take into consideration in order to improve the biodiversity of riparian forests.

And you, what can you do?

Don't damage the plants or dispose of waste

Enjoy riverside areas with respect

Keep to the signposted tracks

Don't release any non-native fauna into the wild

Take part in volunteering campaigns

Report any offences affecting the natural or urban environment

GOOD STATE OF CONSERVATION

Illustration: Anthesis Lavola.

6.

GLOSSARY

White willow catkins (*Salix alba*) on the banks of the Segre River in Cerdanya. / Photo: Jordi Camprodon.

Alder planted and already well established on the banks of the Congost River, in Granollers (Vallès Oriental county) / Photo: Jordi Bas.

6. GLOSSARY

Adaptive management: iterative process in which management actions are followed by specific monitoring. It is a continuous learning process aimed at increasing the capacity for adaptation of ecosystems or species.

Alluvial plain: plain filled with alluvial or fluvial sediments, which may form a set of stepped fluvial terraces.

Aquatic macroinvertebrates: group of animals without an internal skeleton, larvae and adults of insects and other aquatic groups, of very small size: greater than 0.5 mm and more than 500 microns, visible to the naked eye.

Aquifer: an underground formation of water-bearing, permeable rock that allows the storage and circulation of groundwater that may naturally emerge on the surface of the Earth or that may be extracted using wells.

Biological corridor: area that provides connectivity between natural spaces and facilitates, among other ecological processes, migration and genetic exchange between populations of species.

Biological diversity (or biodiversity): variety of living beings, whether between different species (taxonomic diversity), within a species (genetic diversity) or within a particular ecosystem.

Biological indicator or bioindicator: species or group of species that clearly reflect the status of the environment, the impact produced on a habitat, community or ecosystem, as well as indicating the biodiversity of a habitat in general.

Change factors: disturbances that constitute positive or negative impacts on the ecosystem.

Clear cutting: practice in which all the trees in a certain area are cut down at the same time.

Coppice (or low forest): forest regenerated from shoots formed at the stumps of the previous crop trees, suckers or both. Generally speaking, at least 80% of the specimens must originate from shoots.

Coppice (forest) with standards: forest consisting partly of vegetative shoots and partly of trees of seedling origin.

Decay: lack of strength, resilience or vigour, in this case of a plant species.

Diffuse pollution: pollution generated in the aquatic environment by pollutants with no specific point of origin, or pollution generated on large surface areas that is difficult to control and detect.

Earthen berm: flood defence consisting of a mound or embankment of earth, with the necessary retaining structures to stop water.

Ecological resilience: ability of an ecosystem to withstand a disturbance and recover to the point of returning to its prior status, once the disturbance has ceased.

Ecological resistance: process of assisting the recovery of an ecosystem that has been degraded, damaged, or destroyed. Active restoration involves intervening deliberately, intensively or simply channelling natural regeneration. Passive restoration basically consists of stopping change factors and waiting for the site to recover without human intervention and only through natural regeneration processes. This is not always possible, since the deterioration of the ecosystem must not be too extensive to prevent it from recovering by means of its own resources or those provided by adjacent areas.

Ecological status: unification of aspects related to the structure and functioning of aquatic ecosystems; in line with the Water Framework Directive, it is measured according to five levels of quality, from very good to bad.

Ecosystem function: while ecological functioning (the set of ecological processes) is inherent to the intrinsic properties of ecosystems, ecosystem function is understood from a cultural perspective as the capacity of an ecosystem to provide services to satisfy society's needs. Examples include climate regulation, the supply of natural resources, landscape or aesthetic functions, etc.

Environmental flow: minimum flow that must be maintained in a water course in order to sustain its ecosystems.

Extraordinary flood: episode that occurs less frequently than an ordinary flood and that involves a major increase in the flow rate of a river.

Global change: set of changes in the global environment comprising five key components: climate change, alterations of biogeochemical cycles, land use and cover change (LUCC), changes in biodiversity and biological invasions.

Governance: governing practices aimed at achieving lasting economic, social and institutional development, fostering a balance between government and civil society.

Habitat fragmentation: process through which a large expanse of habitat is transformed into smaller fragments that are isolated from each other by a landscape matrix with different properties to that of the original habitat. For example, forest fragments in an agricultural matrix. The process usually involves alterations in the functioning of the habitat and in the composition of species.

Habitats of Community Importance (HCI): a selection of the natural habitats of the European Union (EU). Their conservation within the borders of the EU must be ensured through the creation of a network of protected areas: the Natura 2000 Network.

High forest (or seeding forest): a type of forest originated from seed or from planted seedlings. Generally speaking, at least 80% of the specimens must be regenerated or originate from seed.

Hydromorphological indicator: physical and biological elements that make it possible to characterise a fluvial ecosystem and evaluate its ecological status. For example, its water regime, circulating flow and riparian vegetation.

Hydromorphological restoration: restoring the natural processes of the fluvial system, including its transport functions, dynamics and mobility, as well as recovering sediments, water and banks that generate a complex structure (an ecosystem).

Invasive alien species: non-native or exotic species that becomes established in an ecosystem or habitat; it is an agent of change and threatens native biological diversity. An exotic species (allochthonous, foreign) is one that is found outside its natural range (past or present) and potential dispersal area. A native (or autochthonous) species is one that is found within its natural range and potential dispersal area.

Maturity: applied to a forest (normally called in English ancient or old growth forest), it is understood as an advanced stage of natural succession where numerous trees are old enough to begin to decay, to form dead wood or to open clearings that will allow the regeneration of the forest.

Natural dynamics: set of continuous processes or changes that take place in an ecosystem, formed by the physical environment (lithology, soil) and its biotic components (bacteria, fungi, plants, animals, etc.).

Naturalness: quality of a free-flowing ecosystem, without human influence; in a highly natural ecosystem, the human footprint is barely discernible or non-existent.

Nature-based silviculture: silvicultural theory and practice that considers the forest as an ecosystem. It is based on reduced human intervention and aimed at accelerating natural processes.

Ordinary maximum flood: average of the maximum annual volumes produced over ten consecutive years in the natural flow regime of the river.

Propagule: vegetative structure (such as a bud, sucker or spore) that can become detached from a plant in order to reproduce a new plant.

Public Water Domain (PWD): set of continental surface waters, natural stream beds, the beds of lakes, lagoons and surface reservoirs, and underground aquifers. The purpose of the PWD is to ensure the protection of water resources and their ecosystem. It is defined on the basis of the historical maximum ordinary flooding level of a river.

Riparian forest: forested area of land adjacent to a water course or body of water.

Riparian vegetation: the vegetation hosted by banks and margins of river courses or bodies of water, influenced by the flow regime and the water table.

Rip-rap: set of large stones or blocks arranged next to the water along riverbanks, forming a defensive dyke for flood protection.

River ecosystem: system formed by a water course and its banks or floodplain, including its sediments, soil, water table and biota (microorganisms, flora and fauna), as well as its drainage network.

Selective logging (or thinning): practice of cutting down a few trees or groups of trees in a forest, always maintaining a minimum forest cover level.

Special Area of Conservation: area of importance for the conservation of biodiversity in the European Union, included in the Natura 2000 Network.

Sucker cutback: action through which stump shoots of non-commercial diameters are cleared away, with the aim of enhancing the growth of those that will remain standing.

Sustainable forest management (SFM): management and use of forests in a way designed to maintain their biodiversity, productivity, regeneration capacity and vitality, along with their potential to fulfil, both now and in the future, important ecological, economic and social functions, on a local, national and global scale, without causing damage to other ecosystems.

Systematic planning: applied to nature conservation, it is a process for the identification and selection of natural areas, factors or processes that enables decision-making to be carried out in an efficient, inclusive, repeatable and transparent manner.

Tree injection: an alternative method of phytosanitary treatment of trees, with a low environmental impact

Water table: upper part of an aquifer; that is, rock formations saturated with water.

7.

RECOMMENDED READING

Grey herons (*Ardea cinerea*) nesting in an alder forest of the Ter River in Torelló / Photo: Jordi Bas.

7. RECOMMENDED READING

- / Calleja, J. A. 2009. 91E0 Bosques aluviales arbóreos y arborescentes de cursos generalmente altos y medios, dominados o codominados por alisos (*Alnus glutinosa*), fresnos de montaña (*Fraxinus excelsior*), abedules (*Betula alba* o *B. pendula*), avellanos (*Corylus avellana*) o álamos negros (*Populus nigra*) (*). Ministerio de Medio Ambiente, y Medio Rural y Marino. Madrid.

- / Camprodon, J., Ferreira, M. T., Ordeix, M. (eds.). 2012. *Restauración y gestión ecológica fluvial. Un manual de buenas prácticas de gestión de ríos y riberas*. Centre Tecnològic Forestal de Catalunya & ISA Press. Solsona – Lisboa.

- / Camprodon, J., Guardis, P., Ordeix, M. (eds.). 2022. *Technical handbook for the conservation and restoration of riparian areas. LIFE ALNUS*. Centre de Ciència i Tecnologia Forestal de Catalunya. Programa Life Natura i Biodiversitat de la Unió Europea.

- / Carreras, J., Ferré, J., Vigo, J. 2015. *Manual dels hàbitats de Catalunya. Volum VI. Boscors*. Generalitat de Catalunya, Departament de Territori i Sostenibilitat. Barcelona.

- / Elosegui, A., Sabater, S. (eds.). 2009. *Conceptos y técnicas en ecología fluvial*. Fundación BBVA. Bilbao.

- / Godé, L. (dir.). 2008. *La gestió i recuperació de la vegetació de ribera. Guia tècnica per actuacions en riberes*. Agència Catalana de l'Aigua. Departament de Medi Ambient i Habitatge de la Generalitat de Catalunya. Barcelona.

- / Lara, F., Garilleti, R., Calleja, J. A. 2004. *La vegetación de ribera de la mitad norte de España*. Centro de Estudios de Técnicas Aplicadas del CEDEX. Madrid.

- / Mola, I., Sopeña, A., de Torre, R. (eds.). 2018. *Guía Práctica de Restauración Ecológica*. Fundación Biodiversidad del Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica. Madrid.

- / Munné, A.; Prat, N., Ordeix, M., Puértolas, L., Rieradevall, M. 2009. *Els espais fluvials. Manual de diagnosi ambiental*. Obra Social “La Caixa” i Diputació de Barcelona. Barcelona.

- / Munné, A.; Solà, C., Pagès, J. (eds.). 2006. HIDRI. Protocol d'avaluació de la qualitat hidromorfològica dels rius. Agència Catalana de l'Aigua, Departament de Medi Ambient i Habitatge, Generalitat de Catalunya. Barcelona (disponible a <https://aca.gencat.cat/ca/laigua/seguiment-i-control/protocols>).

/ SER. 2019. *International principles and standards for the practice of ecological restoration*. Society for Ecological Restoration.

/ Vayreda, J., Comas, Ll., Guinart, D., Solórzano, S., Grau, J. 2022. *Manual de buenas prácticas forestales en espacios fluviales*. Parc Natural i Reserva de la Biosfera del Montseny. LIFE Tritó Montseny.

WEB SITES

- / AMBER river project: <https://amber.international/>
- / Atlas of barriers in European rivers: <https://amber.international/european-barrier-atlas/>
- / Blue rivers Foundation: <https://blueriversfoundation.org/>
- / Iberian Centre for River Restoration (CIREF): <https://cirefluvial.com>
- / Dam Removal Europe: <https://damremoval.eu/>
- / European Center for River Restoration: <https://www.ecrr.org/>
- / Open Rivers programme: restoring european rivers: <https://openrivers.eu/>
- / RiverWiki: https://restorerivers.eu/wiki/index.php?title=Main_Page
- / Society for Ecological Restoration: <https://www.ser.org/>
- / Wetlands International: <https://europe.wetlands.org>

River and forest. The Segre River in Cerdanya county / Photo: Jordi Bas.

www.lifealnus.eu

Collaborators

